

Original article

Ocular cancer profile by age in northeastern Nigeria

Rufai Yunusa,^{1,2} Priscilla O. Onoto,^{1,2} Gabriel Sofoluwe,^{1,2} Uchenna S. Ezenkwa,^{1,2} Danjuma A. Maji,^{3,4} Abdulgafar A. Jimoh,^{1,2} Maimuna O. Yusuf,^{5,6} Bello A. Ibrahim,^{5,6} E D. Suleiman,⁷ A Kabir,^{8,9} M. A. Kolomi,^{8,9} A. I. Adamu,¹⁰ Aliyu I. Lawan.^{12,13}

¹ Department of Histopathology, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital Azare
² Department of Anatomic Pathology, Federal University of Health Sciences Azare. ³ Department of Ophthalmology, Federal University of Health Sciences. ⁴ Department of Ophthalmology, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria. ⁵ Department of Paediatrics, Faculty of Clinical Sciences, Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare. ⁶ Department of Paediatrics, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare. ⁷ Department of Histopathology, College of Medical Sciences, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Bauchi State, Nigeria. ⁸ Department of Histopathology, College of Medical Sciences, University of Maiduguri. ⁹ Department of Histopathology, University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Borno State. ¹⁰ Department of Pathology, Federal Medical Centre Nguru, Yobe State, Nigeria. ¹¹ Department of Histopathology, Yobe State University/Yobe State University Teaching Hospital, Yobe State, Nigeria. ¹² Department of Histopathology, College of Medical Sciences, Gombe State University. ¹³ Department of Histopathology, Federal Teaching Hospital, Gombe State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: Dr. Rufai Yunusa. Department of Anatomic Pathology, Federal University of Health Sciences/Federal Medical Centre, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria. Email address: rufai.yunusa@fuhhsa.edu.ng Tel No. +2348036387138

Abstract

Background: Ocular cancer, although rare globally, exhibits the highest incidence in sub-Saharan Africa. Delays in diagnosis and care are thought to contribute to the region's high mortality rates. In Nigeria, it remains an understudied area, complicating policy intervention. The objective of this study was to define the multi-institutional, region-wide profile of ocular malignancies by age in northeastern Nigeria. **Materials and Methods.** We reviewed data on patient age, sex, tumour site, and histological subtype from pathology records and cancer databases of six tertiary hospitals in northeastern Nigeria (Borno, Gombe, Yobe, and Bauchi states) from January 2019 to December 2022. Descriptive statistics and Mann-Whitney U tests were used to determine the proportions of categorical variables and differences in age distribution between paediatric and adult tumours, respectively. A two-tailed significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Sixty-two (62) cases of primary ocular malignancy were documented out of 4681 cancers diagnosed during the study period 1.3%, with a median age of 14 years (IQR 36 years). Most tumours occurred in the eyeball, 40.3% ($n=25$), and conjunctiva, 25.8% ($n=17$). The paediatric age group (<17 years) accounted for 54.8% ($n=34$) of cases, with retinoblastoma the most common (70.6%, 24/34). In adults, squamous cell carcinoma was most common (71.4%, 20/28). A significant age difference was observed between childhood and adult cancers ($p < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** The study found relatively few cases of ocular malignancy, with clear age-related differences in tumour types. The low numbers in this hospital-based series likely underestimate the true community burden, highlighting the need for population-based cancer registries.

Keywords: Delay in diagnosis, Histopathology, Ocular cancer.

Open Access article distribution in the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC by 4.0)

Copyright: The Author(s). 2026

ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20668172>

Date Submitted: 20th February 2026

Date Accepted: 2nd April 2026

Date Published Online: 12th June 2026

Cite this article as: Rufai Yunusa, Priscilla O. Onoto, Gabriel Sofoluwe, Uchenna S. Ezenkwa, Danjuma A. Maji,⁴ Abdulgafar A. Jimoh, Maimuna O. Yusuf, Bello A. Ibrahim, E D. Suleiman, A Kabir, M. A. Kolomi, A. I. Adamu, Aliyu I. Lawan. Ocular cancer profile by age in northeastern Nigeria. *The Scholar J Health Sci* 2026; 2(1): 163-169.

Introduction

Ocular cancer is a rare malignancy worldwide, with an estimated global incidence of 1-11 cases per million.^{1,2} Retinoblastoma and squamous cell carcinoma are the most common encountered malignancies in children less than 5 years of age and adults respectively.^{3,4} In Africa, however, incidence rates are markedly elevated, particularly for ocular surface squamous neoplasia (OSSN), reaching 3-10 times higher than in Europe or North America due to factors like ultraviolet exposure, HIV prevalence, and delayed diagnosis.⁵⁻⁸ This regional burden contributes to poor survival. Studies have shown

that 1-year survival for African retinoblastoma is 78% compared to over 95% in high-income countries.^{9,10}

In Nigeria, ocular tumours constitute about 0.1- 1% of all cancers, yet show distinct age patterns: retinoblastoma dominates in children (up to 52.9% of cases), while conjunctival squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) prevails in adults (35.3%), often linked to HIV.^{11,12} Systematic reviews confirm malignant tumours exceed benign ones nationally, with retinoblastoma and SCC as the top subtypes across decades.¹³ Retinoblastoma, which is the most common childhood ocular tumour, is associated with a relatively poor prognosis.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ Retinoblastoma in Nigerian children primarily arises from germline or somatic mutations in the RB1 on chromosome 13q14, a tumour suppressor gene which regulates cell cycle progression. Hereditary forms (often bilateral) account for about 40% of cases.¹⁸ Prenatal exposures such as pesticides, diagnostic X-rays, maternal use of insecticides, or paternal occupations in welding/machining have been implicated as environmental contributors to the development of paediatric retinoblastoma, though evidence is limited.^{3,19,20} North-eastern Nigeria, including states like Borno, Yobe, Gombe, and Bauchi, remains particularly understudied despite high regional cancer loads and conflict-related care barriers, as evidenced by limited histopathologic data. These disparities underscore the need for region-specific profiles to inform policy, as care delays drive high morbidity and mortality in paediatric cases. This multi-institutional study addresses this gap by analysing age-stratified profiles of ocular malignancies across six tertiary hospitals in north-eastern Nigeria.

Materials and methods

A retrospective, descriptive study was conducted to review histologically diagnosed cases of ocular malignancies from January 2019 to December 2022. Data were sourced from cancer registries and the Histopathology departmental records. Four states of north-eastern Nigeria – namely the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (Borno), Yobe State University Teaching Hospital (Yobe), Federal Medical Centre Nguru (Yobe), Federal Medical Centre Azare (Bauchi), Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (Bauchi), and Federal Teaching Hospital Gombe (Gombe). A data proforma was used to collect information on patient age, sex, tumour site/topography, and histological subtype. The data were reviewed for accuracy and consistency by pathologists at each location; when discrepancies arose, the original haematoxylin and eosin-stained slides were re-examined, and the data were adjusted accordingly. If H&E slides were unavailable, formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissue blocks were retrieved, sectioned, stained with H&E, and evaluated microscopically. The collected data were entered into an Excel spreadsheet and subsequently analysed using SPSS version 20. Descriptive statistics were used to calculate proportions for categorical variables, and the Mann-Whitney U test was used to assess significant differences in age distributions between paediatric and adult tumours at a two-tailed significance level of <0.05. The study adhered to the ethical principles of the World Medical Association for medical research involving human participants, with ethical approval obtained from each participating institution.

All data were anonymised before analysis, and no direct contact with patients was made, so individual consent was not required. Inclusion and exclusion criteria All histologically diagnosed ocular cancers diagnosed during the study period were included. Cases that were excluded include: Cases with missing or damaged blocks and cases with insufficient clinical information, particularly bio data.

Results

A total of 62 cancer cases were documented out of 4681 cancers diagnosed within the period, 1.3% (n=62). Median age was 14 years (IQR 36 years) with a male-to-female ratio of 1.8:1. 54.8% (n=34) were ≤17 years old. A total of 62 ocular malignancies were identified during the study period, comprising 34 paediatric cases (≤17 years) and 28 adult cases (>17 years), as shown in Table 1. Retinoblastoma was the most common malignancy in the paediatric population, accounting for 24 of the 34 paediatric cases (70.6%), but was rare in adults, with only one case recorded. The difference in the overall age distribution between the two groups was statistically significant (Mann-Whitney U test, p < 0.001). Other paediatric tumours included rhabdomyosarcoma (4 cases), non-Hodgkin lymphoma (2 cases), squamous cell carcinoma (2 cases), mucoepidermoid carcinoma (1 case), and small round blue cell tumour (1 case).

Adult ocular malignancies were dominated by epithelial tumours, particularly squamous cell carcinoma, which accounted for 18 of the 28 adult cases (64.3%), making it the most frequent malignancy in this age group. Additional tumours seen among adults included basal cell carcinoma (2 cases), carcinoma in situ (2 cases), melanoma (1 case), low-grade adnexal tumour (1 case), carcinoma (1 case), non-Hodgkin lymphoma (1 case), mucoepidermoid carcinoma (1 case), and a single case of retinoblastoma.

The anatomical distribution of ocular cancers is illustrated in Figure 1A. Tumours involved various ocular and peri-ocular structures, including the globe, conjunctiva, eyelid and adnexal tissues. Lesions involving the globe were

predominantly seen in the paediatric age group, while conjunctival and eyelid tumours were more frequent among adults.

The histological spectrum of the tumours is presented in Figure 1B. The lesions included retinoblastoma, rhabdomyosarcoma, non-Hodgkin lymphoma, squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), basal cell carcinoma (BCC), carcinoma in situ (CIN), melanoma, mucoepidermoid carcinoma, small round blue cell tumour (SRBCT), and low-grade adnexal neoplasm

Table 1: Cancer distribution by age

Histologic cancer type	Paediatric Age ≤17 years	Adult (>17 years)
Retinoblastoma	24	1
Rhabdomyosarcoma	4	--
Non-Hodgkin lymphoma	2	1
Mucoepidermoid carcinoma	1	1
SCC	2	18
SRBCT	1	-
Carcinoma in-situ	-	2
Melanoma	-	1
Low grade adnexal tumour	-	1
Carcinoma, NOS	-	1
Basal cell carcinoma	-	2
Total	34	28

NOS= Not otherwise specified

Figure 1A: Parts of the eye affected by cancer

Figure 1B: Histological classification of ocular cancers seen. SCC: Squamous cell carcinoma; BCC: Basal cell carcinoma; CIN: carcinoma in-situ; SRBCT: small round blue cell tumour, LGAN: Low-grade adnexal neoplasm

Discussion

The results demonstrated that ocular cancers accounted for 1.3% of all documented malignancies in this study. This proportion is higher than the 0.5% reported in India and the 0.1% reported in a systematic review in Nigeria.^{9,10} This disparity may reflect the specific referral patterns to these tertiary centres or, more likely, the significant under-diagnosis and under-reporting of other more common cancers (e.g., breast, cervical, prostate) in this region, which would inflate the relative proportion of ocular tumours

A male predominance was observed, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.8:1, which is consistent with the 2.4:1 ratio reported in North-Western Nigeria.^{9,21} The reason for this male preponderance is not entirely clear but may relate to gender-based differences in health-seeking behaviour, occupational exposure (particularly to ultraviolet radiation), or sociocultural factors influencing access to care.

The median age of 14 years in this study is comparable to findings from Kano (13.4 years) but differs significantly from reports in Lagos (22.9 years) and Benin (26 years).^{9,11,12} These variations may be attributed to differences in sociodemographic characteristics, referral patterns, environmental exposures, and the relative contribution of paediatric versus adult malignancies across study locations.

The findings demonstrate a clear age-related variation in the pattern of ocular malignancies, with retinoblastoma predominating in children, while squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) and other epithelial tumours were more common in adults. This distribution is consistent with previous studies.^{9,11,13} Systematic reviews and tertiary hospital series similarly report that malignant tumours constitute a substantial proportion of orbito-ocular lesions, with retinoblastoma and conjunctival SCC being the most frequent malignancies in paediatric and adult populations, respectively.¹⁴ The relatively high proportion of retinoblastoma among paediatric cases (70.6%) and adult SCC (64.3%) in this cohort aligns with prior reports, although the proportion of SCC may be higher than that observed in some Western populations. This difference may be explained by increased ultraviolet exposure, delayed presentation, limited access to early ophthalmic care, and the study's hospital-based design.¹⁵

The predominance of small round blue cell tumours in this study, consistent with other reports, suggests an important role for germline and early-life genetic aberrations in the pathogenesis of ocular malignancies.⁷ Small, round, blue tumours of the orbit have their distinct genetic drivers. In particular, retinoblastoma is known to arise from biallelic mutations in the RB1 tumour suppressor gene (chromosome 13q14.2), leading to dysregulated cell-cycle control and tumour development.⁷ Other SRBCTs, such as alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma, are characterised by distinct genetic drivers like PAX3/7-FOXO1 fusions.^{7,22,23} This underscores the importance of genetic mechanisms in paediatric ocular cancers and highlights the potential value of genetic counselling and early screening in at-risk populations.

Limitation

This study has some limitations as a retrospective, hospital-based design means the findings cannot be used to calculate true population-based incidence rates. The 62 cases represent only those patients who reached a tertiary facility and received a histological diagnosis. Second, due to the nature of registry data, we lacked critical clinical information, including HIV status, stage at presentation, treatment details, and outcomes, which are essential for a complete clinical picture. Third, while we attempted to verify diagnoses, the small sample size limits the power for more detailed subgroup analyses. Finally, accurate classification of certain tumours, particularly small round blue cell tumours and low-grade adnexal neoplasms, was limited by the lack of immunohistochemistry, which would have significantly aided diagnosis in these and other challenging cases.

Conclusion

Our findings demonstrate a relatively low number of documented ocular malignancies in this population, with clear age-related differences in histological subtypes. However, the limited case numbers observed in this hospital-based series likely underestimate the true burden of disease in the wider community. This underscores the need for more comprehensive and systematic data collection through well-established population-based cancer registries to accurately define the epidemiology of ocular malignancies.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, it is recommended that early detection strategies for ocular malignancies be strengthened, particularly by integrating routine paediatric eye screening into primary healthcare services and immunisation programmes. In addition, community-based awareness campaigns should be intensified to educate caregivers on early warning signs – such as leukocoria, proptosis, and persistent ocular masses – and to promote timely presentation to healthcare facilities.

Furthermore, there is a need for well-designed population-based or multi-centre studies to better characterise the epidemiology of ocular cancers in the region. Future research should

focus on elucidating key risk factors, including ultraviolet radiation exposure, infectious agents, and genetic predisposition, and on evaluating cost-effective screening and intervention strategies suitable for resource-limited settings. Strengthening diagnostic capacity, including histopathology and ancillary techniques, will also be essential in improving patient outcomes.

Financial support and sponsorship

Nil.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Global Retinoblastoma Study Group, Fabian ID, Abdallah E, Abdullahi SU, Abdulqader RA, Adamou Boubacar S, et al. Global Retinoblastoma Presentation and Analysis by National Income Level. *JAMA Oncol.* 2020; 6(5):685. doi:10.1001/jamaoncol.2019.6716
2. Gichuhi S, Sagoo MS, Weiss HA, Burton MJ. Epidemiology of ocular surface squamous neoplasia in Africa. *Trop Med Int Health.* 2013; 18(12):1424–43. doi:10.1111/tmi.12203
3. Byroju VV, Nadukkandy AS, Cordani M, Kumar LD. Retinoblastoma: present scenario and future challenges. *Cell Commun Signal.* 2023; 21(1):226. doi:10.1186/s12964-023-01223-z
4. Fasina O, Fawole OI, Ayeni OA. Orbito-Ocular Tumours in Ibadan, South-West Nigeria. *West Afr J Med.* 2014; 33(3):211–5. PubMed PMID: 26070827.
5. Koochakzadeh L, Hashemi H, Noor Research Center for Ophthalmic Epidemiology, Noor Eye Hospital, Tehran 1983963113, Iran, Pakzad R, Department of Epidemiology, Faculty of Health, Ilam University of Medical Sciences, Ilam 6931851147, Iran, et al. Epidemiological aspect of retinoblastoma in the world: a review of recent advance studies. *Int J Ophthalmol.* 2023; 16(6):962–8. doi:10.18240/ijo.2023.06.20

6. Fabian ID, Stacey AW, Foster A, Kivelä TT, Munier FL, Keren-Froim N, et al. Travel burden and clinical presentation of retinoblastoma: analysis of 1024 patients from 43 African countries and 518 patients from 40 European countries. *Br J Ophthalmol*. 2021; 105(10):1435–43. doi:10.1136/bjophthalmol-2020-316613
7. Ogbonna GO, Chikhoza M, Kwarteng MA, Ezinne NE, Ehigbor R, Anyatonwu OP, et al. Epidemiology of oculo-orbital tumours in Malawian children: a 10-year review of cases from tertiary hospitals. *BMC Ophthalmol*. 2025; 25(1):245. doi:10.1186/s12886-025-04091-y
8. Sinyiza FW, Chisale MRO, Kayira AB, Chimbatata CS, Kaseka PU, Kamudumuli P, et al. Histopathological profile of orbito-ocular cancers at a tertiary hospital in Northern Malawi: a retrospective cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open Ophthalmol*. 2022; 7(1):e000977. doi:10.1136/bmjophth-2022-000977 PubMed PMID: 35402729; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC8948413.
9. Nishath T, Stacey AW, Steinberg D, Foster A, Bowman R, Essuman V, et al. Retinoblastoma survival and enucleation outcomes in 41 countries from the African continent. *Br J Ophthalmol*. 2025; 109(1):64–9. doi:10.1136/bjo-2023-324746
10. Parkin DM, Stefan C. Editorial: Childhood Cancer in sub-Saharan Africa. *ecancermedalscience*. 2017; 11. doi:10.3332/ecancer.2017.ed69
11. Fasina O. Ocular surface squamous neoplasia at a tertiary eye facility, Southwestern Nigeria: a 10-year review. *Int Ophthalmol*. 2021; 41(10):3325–31. doi:10.1007/s10792-021-01894-y
12. Nathaniel GI, Eze UA, Onwuegbuna AA, Echih CI, Alen HA. Pattern of Orbito-ocular Tumours in Nigeria: a systematic review. *BMC Cancer*. 2025; 25(1):224. doi:10.1186/s12885-025-13603-4
13. Nathaniel GI, Eze UA, Onwuegbuna AA, Echih CI, Alen HA. Pattern of Orbito-ocular Tumours in Nigeria: a systematic review. *BMC Cancer*. 2025; 25(1):224. doi:10.1186/s12885-025-13603-4 PubMed PMID: 39922999; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC11806794.
14. Kruger M, Van Elsland SL, Davidson A, Stones D, Du Plessis J, Naidu G, et al. Outcome of Retinoblastoma After Implementation of National Retinoblastoma Treatment Guidelines in South Africa. *JCO Glob Oncol*. 2024; 10:e2400034. doi:10.1200/GO.24.00034
15. Stefan DC. Childhood Cancer in Africa: An Overview of Resources. *J Pediatr Hematol Oncol*. 2015; 37(2):104–8. doi:10.1097/MPH.000000000000111
16. Waddell K, Matua M, Bidwell C, Atwine R, Onyango J, Picton SV, et al. A ten-year study of Retinoblastoma in Uganda: An approach to improving outcome with limited resources. *Cancer Epidemiol*. 2021; 71:101777. doi:10.1016/j.canep.2020.101777
17. Lukamba RM, Yao JJA, Kabesha TA, Budiongo AN, Monga BB, Mwembo AT, et al. Retinoblastoma in Sub-Saharan Africa: Case Studies of the Republic of Côte d'Ivoire and the Democratic Republic of the Congo. *J Glob Oncol*. 2018 Dec;(4):1–8. doi:10.1200/JGO.17.00056
18. Abu-Amero KK, Kondkar AA, Almontashiri NAM, Khan AM, Maktabi AMY, Hameed S, et al. Genetics of Retinoblastoma: An Overview and Significance of Genetic Testing in Clinical Practice. *Genes*. 2025; 16(9):1031. doi:10.3390/genes16091031
19. Alabi AO, Alabi AS, Sowunmi AC, Ololade KO, Adegboyega BC, Habeebu MYM, et al. Presentation and Management of Orbito-Ocular Malignancies in a Tertiary Institution in Southwest Nigeria. *J West Afr Coll Surg*. 2023; 13(1):1–5. doi:10.4103/jwas.jwas_37_21
20. Thompson S, Ritz B, Cockburn M, Heck JE. Prenatal ambient pesticide exposure and childhood retinoblastoma. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2022; 245:114025. doi:10.1016/j.ijheh.2022.114025
21. Sunderraj P. Malignant tumours of the eye and adnexa. *Indian J Ophthalmol*. 1991; 39(1):6–8. PubMed PMID: 1894347.
22. Pancaldi A, Peng L, Rhee DS, Dunn E, Forcucci JA, Belchis D, et al. DICER1-associated metastatic abdominopelvic

primitive neuroectodermal tumor with an EWSR1 rearrangement in a 16-yr-old female. Cold Spring Harb Mol Case Stud. 2020; 6(5):a005603. doi:10.1101/mcs.a005603 PubMed PMID: 33028642; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC7552927.

23. Brohl AS, Patidar R, Turner CE, Wen X, Song YK, Wei JS, et al. Frequent inactivating germline mutations in DNA repair genes in patients with Ewing sarcoma. Genet Med Off J Am Coll Med Genet. 2017; 19(8):955-8. doi:10.1038/gim.2016.206 PubMed PMID: 28125078; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC5529247.